

BALACHATURBHADRA CHURNA: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW**Vinod Kumar^{1*}, Anupriya^{2*}, Sanju Sharma³, Surender Sharma⁴, Chakravarti⁵**^{*1,3}Ayurvedic Medical Officer, CHC, Gohana, Sonipat.²PhD Scholar, Dept. of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Shri Krishna Ayush University, Kurukshetra.⁴General Practitioner, Sharma Clinic, Rohtak.⁵Ayurvedic Medical Officer (RBSK), CHC, Gohana, Sonipat.

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ABSTRACT

Balachaturbhadra Churna is frequently prescribed by Kaumarbhritya practitioners due to its broad usefulness in paediatric disorders. It comprises Musta, Pippali, Ativisha and Karkatashringi, a combination first described in Chakradatta.^[1] This review compiles classical citations and pharmacological actions of its ingredients, integrating traditional knowledge with scientific understanding.

KEYWORDS: Balachaturbhadra Churna.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda emphasises preventive health and maintenance of balance in body and mind through lifestyle, diet and rational herbal use.^[2] Among classical dosage forms, Churna Kalpana is widely used due to ease of preparation and rapid action.^[3] Many multi-herb formulations exist in paediatric care, but gaps remain regarding detailed mechanisms of action.^[4] Balachaturbhadra Churna is a prominent formulation indicated for respiratory conditions, fever, diarrhoea and vomiting in children.^[5] It consists of four herbs—Musta, Pippali, Ativisha and Karkatashringi—uniformly described across classical texts including Chakradatta and Sharangadhara Samhita.^[1,6]

Table 1: Balachaturbhadra Churna in Classical Texts.

Sr.No.	Text / Grantha	Reference	Indications	Other Name(s)
1	Cakradatta	64/22	Jwara, Atisara, Vrana, Śwāsa, Vamana	—
2	Gadanigraha	11/93	Jwara, Atisara, Kasa, Śwāsa, Vaman)	—
3	Sharangadhara Samhita	6/16	Jwara, Atisara, Kāsa, Śwāsa, Vamana	Krushṇādi Churna
4	Bhavaprakasha	71/151	Jwara, Atisara, Kāsa, Śwāsa, Vamana	Chaturbhadra Avaleha
5	Yogaratnakara	71/39	Jwara, Atisara, Kāsa, Śwāsa, Vamana	Ghanādi Churna
6	Bhaishajya Ratnavali	71/39	Jwara, Atisara, Kāsa, Śwāsa, Vamana	—
7	Bhaishajya Samhita	7/50	Not specifically mentioned	—
8	Bharat Bhaishajya Ratnakar	7/24	Same as Bhaishajya Ratnavali	—
9	Bala Tantra / Kaumarbhritya Grantha	13/10	Jwara, Atisara, Kāsa, Śwāsa, Vamana	Balachaturbhadraka Churna
10	Ayurvedic Formulary of India (AFI)	Part I / p. 92	Classical pediatric use: Jwara, Atisara, Kasa, Śwāsa, Chardi	Balachaturbhadra Churna

Table 2: Ingredients of Balchaturbhadra Churna.

Ingredient	Latin Name	Family	Part Used	Proportion
Ativisha	Aconitum heterophyllum	Ranunculaceae	Root	1 part
Shringi (Karkatashringi)	Pistacia integerrima	Anacardiaceae	Gall	1 part
Pippali	Piper longum	Piperaceae	Fruit	1 part
Musta	Cyperus rotundus	Cyperaceae	Rhizome	1 part

Table 3: Ayurvedic Pharmacological Profile And Properties Of Medicinal Plants In Balchaturbhadra Churna.

Parameter	Ativisha	Shringi	Pippali	Musta
Rasa	Katu, Tikta	Tikta, Kashaya	Katu, Tikta	Katu, Tikta, Kashaya
Guna	-	Guru	Laghu, Snigdha, Ushna	Laghu, Ruksha
Virya	Ushna	Ushna	Anushna	Sheeta
Vipaka	Katu	Katu	Madhura	Katu
Doshagnata	Kapha–Pitta hara	Kapha–Vata hara	Vata–Kapha hara	Kapha–Pitta–Rakta hara

METHOD OF PREPARATION

The rhizome of musta, fruits of Pippali, roots of ativisha, and gall of shringi were collected. Drugs were dried properly by drying, powdered by pulverizer and stored in an air-tight container. The Balchaturbhadra Churna was prepared by mixing the powder of above four ingredients in equal proportions.

Dose: Dose of Balachaturbhadra churna is 1/2 -1 gm as per Bhaisajya Ratnavali.^[7]

Anupana – Honey.

Side Effect

As such no side effects have been reported but high dose may worsen gastritis.

DISCUSSION

The formulation's therapeutic relevance stems from the synergistic roles of its four herbal components. Ativisha and Musta support digestive restoration and reduce metabolic toxins, making them suitable for fever and diarrhea.^[2,3] Shringi and Pippali primarily address respiratory congestion and impaired immunity.^[8,11] Contemporary research highlights anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and antidiarrhoeal activities in these herbs, supporting their classical indications.^[12,14] The persistent mention of this formulation in multiple ancient texts, with consistent composition, reflects longstanding clinical recognition and validates its continued application in paediatric care.^[1,6,10]

CONCLUSION

Balachaturbhadra churna, a polyherbal churna preparation has multiple benefits on various disorders of childrens. It is concluded that mentioned classical references have included same ingredients like ativisha, pippali, musta, karkatashringi in the same proportion and all have indicated it in jwara, atisara, kasa, swasa, vaman except Chakradatta has indicated it in vrana while Yogaratnakara in jwaratisara. Shrangadhara samhita have named it as krushnadi churna while Bhavaprakasha named it as Chaturbhadra avleha. Yogaratnakara and Bala tantra have named it has Ghranadi churna, Balachaturbhadrika churna respectively.

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